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Hcp5 and Hcg11 mark the newborn lymphocyte.

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Hcp5 and Hcg11 expression defined that of the newborn lymphocyte in *Homo sapiens*. HLA histocompatibility antigens Hcg17, Hcg18 and Hcg27 did not change between developmental stage.